

dissociates in two steps as below :

The formation curve of the ligand extends over a range ($0.4 < \bar{n}_d < 1.9$) and indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2L^+ i.e., phenolic hydrogen and protonated nitrogen are completely dissociable. $\log p_{K_1}\text{H}$ and $\log p_{K_2}\text{H}$ belongs to the formation of HL and H_2L^+ species respectively.

The depression of the metal – titration curves below the ligand titration curve at the pH values much below the pH of metal ion hydrolysis confirms the complexation between the ligand and metal ions. The proton of the phenolic OH group has been replaced by the metal and the chelation takes place through phenolate oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

There was no precipitation upto $\text{pH} = 9.25$ for Mn^{2+} and 9.50 for Co^{2+} . The values of $\bar{n}$ obtained were more than 1.0 at higher pH values suggesting 1 : 2 complexation.

The order of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} was $\text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$ which was according to the Irving – Williams rule⁵.

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Studies on Dioctyltin Dithiocarbamates

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IN continuation of our studies on diorganotin dithiocarbamates¹, the present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of a series of new dioctyltin derivatives. Analytical, conductance, molecular weight, thermogravimetric data, IR, PMR and electronic spectral studies have been made to establish the structure of the newly synthesized compounds.

Experimental

Dioctyltin oxide was obtained from Alfa Inorganics (U. S. A.). Amines and solvents were purified by conventional methods². Physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier¹.

The newly synthesized dioctyltin bis (dithiocarbamates) were prepared by insertion of carbon disulphide to amine and dioctyltin oxide mixture, as represented below

A representative experiment for the preparation of dioctyltin bis (dithiocarbamates) is described below.

To a mixture of dioctyltin oxide (10 mmole) and carbon disulphide (10 ml) in chloroform (20 ml) a solution of morpholine (20 mmole) in chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise at -20° . After stirring for about two hrs., excess chloroform was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting brown viscous liquid was extracted with diethyl ether, and the product dried under vacuum (yield 70%).

Results and Discussion

The compounds are yellow to brown, high boiling oily liquids except piperidine and diphenyl derivatives which are sharp melting solids. They are soluble in chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, methanol and dichloromethane. The molecular weight determination in (freezing) benzene (cryoscopic method) and electrical conductance measurements in methanol indicate their monomeric and non-electrolytic behaviour.

Thermogravimetric analysis of dioctyltin bis (piperidine dithiocarbamate) was carried out at a heating rate of $5^\circ/\text{minute}$. Results indicate that it slowly decomposes at -100° liberating carbon disulphide. The residual weight at 260° corresponds to an equimolar mixture of dioctyltin sulphide and bis (piperidine) thiourea,

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR DIOCTYL TIN DITHIOCARBAMATES $[(C_8H_{17})_2Sn(dtc)_2]$

dtc.	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			Infrared absorption frequencies in cm^{-1}	
		Sn	C	H	ν C-N	ν C-S
morpholine	653 (669)	17.74 (17.79)	46.60 (46.64)	7.43 (7.47)	1471 vs 1449 vs	1030 vs 1010 s
piperidine*	655 (665)	17.65 (17.89)	50.61 (50.53)	8.20 (8.12)	1471 vs 1449 s	996 s 977 s
diethyl	632 (641)	18.52 (18.56)	48.69 (48.67)	8.38 (8.42)	1481 vs 1471 sh	990 s 985 s
di-n-propyl	685 (697)	17.10 (17.07)	51.62 (51.65)	8.79 (8.90)	1481 s 1460 sh	1010 m 980 s
di-n-butyl	741 (753)	15.83 (15.80)	54.21 (54.18)	9.26 (9.30)	1481 vs 1471 sh	1010 s 980 m
pyrrolidine	623 (637)	18.62 (18.68)	49.01 (48.98)	7.78 (7.85)	1471 s 1449 vs	1008 vs 980 m
N-methylaniline	697 (709)	16.75 (16.78)	54.06 (54.16)	7.08 (7.05)	1467 s 1449 vs	1000 vs 984 m
N-ethylaniline	725 (737)	16.19 (16.15)	55.29 (55.36)	7.35 (7.33)	1467 s 1458 vs	1000 s 980 s
dibenzyl	879 (889)	13.41 (13.39)	62.31 (62.09)	6.93 (6.97)	1464 vs 1451 s	1000 s 980 s
diphenyl*	821 (833)	14.33 (14.29)	60.47 (60.50)	6.51 (6.48)	1466 s 1447 m	1020 s 1000 m

* melting point 55°C

Further heating to 440° leaves behind a non-volatile residue identified as tin metal. The pyrolysis of the compound may be represented as follows:

In the infrared spectra of the compounds two absorptions of diagnostic value for C-N and C-S stretching modes of vibration (at $1468 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $1460 \pm 13 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; for ν C-N and $1010 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $990 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ν C-S) indicate monodentate behaviour of the dithiocarbamate groups^{3,4}. A comparison of the spectra of compounds under investigation reveals that ν C-N shifts to a higher value on substituting a heterocyclic group by a dialkyl derivative in the ligand. The shift is attributed to greater electron releasing capacity of the dialkyl substituents than the heterocyclic systems where rigidity of the ring system prevents electron release. Sn-C asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes have been identified at ~ 605 and $\sim 515 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

¹HNMR spectra of the compounds exhibit mainly two groups of signals, one due to N-CH₂ protons at ~ 3.70 and the other due to octyl group in the region (0.80–2.00) δ ppm. A little lower deshielding of N-CH₂ protons, in addition to overlapping of the signals, is indicative of restricted rotation about the C-N bond which makes two groups magnetically non equivalent giving rise to unidentate coordination of the ligand^{5,6}.

The electronic spectra of the compounds studied in the range 200–300 nm show 2 bands at $\sim 250 \text{ nm}$ and $\sim 280 \text{ nm}$ assignable to intraligand transitions. The high energy band ($\sim 250 \text{ nm}$) is connected with $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition located in CS₂ group of the ligand. Presence of an unsplit intense band at $\sim 250 \text{ nm}$ supports the monodentate character of the ligand⁷.

The results indicate that the dioctyltin bis dithiocarbamates possess a tetracoordinated tin atom with monodentate dithiocarbamate ligands arranged in a tetrahedral geometry.

The compounds were tested *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against five fungi *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporium canis*, *Aspergillus niger* and three bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli* by two fold serial dilution

method⁸. In contrast to the high activity of tributyltin dithiocarbamates⁹ the corresponding dioctyltin derivatives fail to arrest the microbial growth to a significant extent.

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Analytical Applications of Copper(II) in Acetonitrile : Determination of Mercaptans

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COPPER(II) is an excellent oxidant in acetonitrile, possessing high redox potential, suitable stability and the ability to oxidise several compounds¹⁻⁷. Verma and Kumar^{8,9} have recently described the use of copper(II) in acetonitrile for the visual and potentiometric determination of xanthates, organotrithiocarbonates and ascorbic acid in acetonitrile medium. The present communication extends the use of this oxidant to the determination of mercaptans in acetonitrile. The oxidation of mercaptans with hydrated copper(II)

perchlorate in acetonitrile medium is fast in the initial stages but becomes slow as the titration proceeds. The determination can however be accomplished by reacting mercaptans with an excess of reagent in acetonitrile and back-titrating its unreacted excess with standard ascorbic acid in the same solvent using diphenylamine or N, N'-diphenylbenzidine as indicator. The end-point in back-titration may also be detected potentiometrically by using a platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode. In visual titrations, the end-point is marked by the sudden disappearance of blue colour. That copper(II) can be smoothly and rapidly titrated with ascorbic acid in acetonitrile medium, has recently been described by Verma and Kumar⁹. The proposed method for the determination of mercaptans is simple, accurate and of wide applications.

Experimental

Acetonitrile: Distilled twice from phosphorus pentoxide (5g/l).

Hydrated copper (II) perchlorate, 0.05N in acetonitrile: Prepared and standardised as described earlier⁹.

Ascorbic acid, 0.05N in acetic acid-acetonitrile: A little more than the calculated amount of the compound was dissolved in minimum quantity of warm acetic acid and the solution was left to attain room temperature, then diluted with acetonitrile to a known volume. The solution was standardised against iodine liberated by the reaction of potassium iodide and potassium iodate.

Mercaptans: n-Butyl, isobutyl, benzyl and dodecyl mercaptans, 2-mercaptoethanol (all Fluka, Switzerland) and thiophenol (Riedel, German) were distilled before use. 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (Fluka) was used as received.

Indicator solutions: Diphenylamine and N, N'-diphenylbenzidine solutions in acetonitrile, 0.10 and 0.05% respectively.

Procedure: To a known volume (3 to 6 ml) of standard (0.05N) hydrated copper (II) perchlorate were added aliquots of the solutions in acetonitrile of each mercaptan. Each solution was diluted with 30 ml of acetonitrile, kept for 3 to 5 minutes, mixed with 1-2 drops of indicator solution and titrated at room temperature (~23°) with standard (0.05N) ascorbic acid in the same solvent. The end-point was marked by the sudden disappearance of blue colour.

From the volume of standard (0.05N) ascorbic acid used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each mercaptan was calculated. The results are given in Table 1.